

WAFER-LEVEL PACKAGING OF MICRO-OPTICS

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ABSTRACT

The continuous effort of OEM manufacturers to reduce manual assembly steps results in a push towards higher integration of micro-lens products with technologies such as wafer-level packaging. A wafer-level adhesive bonding process was developed to precisely connect a micro-lens array wafer to one or two glass spacer wafers. The resulting bond allows a rigid mechanical connection of silicon to glass and a low loss transmission through the stack. To enable volume production of the bonded chip a backend production chain including dicing and automatic inspection was implemented. The reliability of the spacer glass and adhesive combination was proven by a set of datacom specific environmental tests.

KEYWORDS: micro-optics, wafer-level optics, wafer-level bonding, wafer-level packaging, micro-lens array, datacom, telecom, reliability testing, Telcordia

INTRODUCTION

Research on micro-optics dates back to the 1980s after manufacturing processes developed for wafer-level integrated circuits became more widely accessible. The stacking thereof was made popular by Iga et al. in their seminal contribution on stacked planar optics [1].

A state of the art manufacturing process for micro-lenses is the so called reflow & etch process, where photolithographically structured resist pillars are melted to sphere segments and then transferred in to the substrate by reactive ion etching [2].

Axetris AG is a manufacturer of such precision wafer-level micro-optics for tele- and datacom markets as well as for the industrial and medical sectors and serves customers with a wide range of micro-optics products. The product portfolio ranges from refractive micro-optic lenses to diffractive optical elements covering the entire wavelength range from UV to mid-IR.

In modern optical transceivers micro-lenses are precisely aligned and glued to position. In some cases additional glass spacers are attached to the lens chip for packaging and reliability reasons. In this work a wafer-level bonding approach is developed to eliminate manual chip level adhesive connection steps during assembly. The main requirements for this process are the precise and reliable mechanical connection between glass and silicon chip while maintaining a low loss optical transmission normal to the bond surface.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plano convex micro-lens arrays were fabricated using the reflow & etch process on silicon wafers. The strict surface profile specification of the lenses was measured by white light interferometry. Then the silicon lens wafers were coated with an AR-coating. This coating was optimized for lowest NIR reflectivity against the refractive index of the adhesive that was used for wafer-level bonding.

Bonding trials with different UV- and thermal-curing adhesives were performed to identify the most reliable and processable adhesive material. The adhesives were spin coated on the glass spacer substrates to achieve a uniform and precise adhesive thickness across the stack. The stack was then aligned and bonded together in vacuum. As a result from these trials, a UV-curing epoxy with an index of refraction closely matching the one of the glass spacers was chosen for the wafer bonding process, since it required lower bonding temperatures and thus reduced the thermal stress in the material stack as compared to thermal adhesive bonding. Furthermore, this process does not require high bonding pressure to yield a void-free bond. This process was repeated for the opposite side of the lens wafer to fabricate double-side bonded micro-optic wafers.

For the bonded wafers a custom dicing process was developed, allowing the singulation of the wafers with low edge chipping. Quality control of the bonding and dicing process was performed by an automatic visual inspection. Due to the planarity of the substrates the bond interface acts as a mirror for surface defects and can hamper automatic focusing algorithms. Defects that are on the surface seem to be deep below the bondline with an example shown in Figure 1. To reliably inspect the bondline additional passes with optimized automatic focusing were implemented.

The reliability of the bond was evaluated by extensive environmental testing of the bonded chips according to Telcordia GR_1221 standards including 1000 hours damp heat storage.

Figure 1: Real and mirrored defects observed during automated inspection of bonded chips.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Utilizing the wafer-level adhesive bonding process with the selected UV-curing epoxy and the subsequent dicing process the two chip designs from Figure 2 were fabricated. The established inspection process not only allowed the detection of surface defects on the chip front and backside, but was specifically optimized to inspect the bond interfaces through the glass spacer. Microscopic voids and particles were rare, but could be detected reliably with this method. The environmental testing throughout the development process of this product ensured that the selected bonding approach allows a reliable optical and mechanical connection of the spacers to the micro-lens chip. It also showed that spacer glasses have to be chosen with the same caution as the adhesives, because some glasses can corrode in high humidity conditions.

Figure 2: Side view images of the wafer-level bonded chips after dicing.

CONCLUSIONS

With the presented wafer-level adhesive bonding process and the established backend processes Axetris is now able to fabricate higher integrated micro-optics products. This capability allows us to support our customers on the path to more reliable and cost-effective products. In future this process can be extended to more complex designs for example by utilizing structured or metallized glass substrates.

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